

Studies in Spiroheterocycles. Part-XXVI. Investigation of the Reaction of 3-(2-Oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-ones with Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride and Phenylsulphonyl Hydrazide¹

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Reactions of fluorinated 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-ones (**1**) with 4-fluorophenylsulphonyl hydrazide in ethanolic KOH yielded spiro[3*H*-indazole-3,3'-(3*H*)-indole]-2'(1'*H*)-ones (**2a, b**; *n*=2) and spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-(3*H*)-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (**2c**; *n*=1). Further, the reaction of **1** with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in dry pyridine in the presence of fused sodium acetate yielded some new 2,3*a*,4,5,6,7-hexahydro[spiro-3*H*-benzisoxazole-3,3'-(3*H*)-indol]-2'(1'*H*)-one (**3a, b**; *n*=2) and 4',5'-cyclopentasp[iro-3*H*-indole-3,3'-(3*H*)-isoxazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (**3c, d**; *n*=1). The non-fluorinated analog gave 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)-2'-oximeindole-2(1*H*)-one (**4a**) in addition to the spiro compound (**3a**). All the compounds have been characterised from their analytical and ir, pmr, ¹³C nmr, ¹⁹F nmr and mass spectral data.

IN view of our continued interest on biologically active indole derivatives², it was thought worthwhile to incorporate some additional heterocyclic moieties of pharmacological importance, viz. isoxazole, pyrazole and indazole to the indole nuclei through a spiro carbon. Various spiro-pyrazolines, spiroindolinoisoxazoles and benzisoxazoles exhibit biological activities³.

We have earlier studied various cyclocondensation reactions of indolyl-enones, viz. 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-ones (**1**) and 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indole-2-ones^{4,5}. Reaction of **1** with phenyl hydrazines gave spiro compounds, while reaction of 3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indole-2-ones with hydrazine hydrate/phenyl hydrazine/pentafluorophenyl hydrazine yielded the corresponding hydrazone derivative, spiro compounds and pyridazinoindoles depending upon the reaction conditions⁶. No attention has however been paid to the reaction of phenylsulphonyl hydrazide with any of the enone derivatives so far. We have earlier reported the reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride with 3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-indole-2-ones yielding spiroindolinoisoxazoles⁷. A literature survey revealed that the reactions of 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-one with hydroxylamine hydrochloride have not been studied so far. Moreover, cyclocondensation reaction of 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-ones seems to be interesting as these oxindoline derivatives possess two α,β -unsaturated carbonyl systems involving carbonyl group of indole ring and carbonyl group of cycloalkane ring⁸. Further, cyclocondensation involving both the unsaturated carbonyl systems is also possible⁹.

In view of such observations, we have studied the reactions of 4-fluorophenylsulphonyl hydrazide and hydroxylamine hydrochloride with fluorinated 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-one (**1**). Reaction of 4-fluorophenylsulphonyl hydrazide with **1** (*n*=1 or 2) yielded exclusively spiro compounds in contrast to our earlier observation of the formation of a mixture of products⁶, viz. hydrazone, pyridazinoindoles and spiro compound. Reaction with **1** (*n*=1) yielded 4',5'-cyclopenta-2'-(4-fluorophenylsulphonyl)spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-(3*H*)-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (**2c**) and that with **1** (*n*=2) gave 2,3*a*,4,5,6,7-hexahydro-2-(4-fluorophenylsulphonyl)spiro[3*H*-indazole-3,3'-(3*H*)-indol]-2'(1'*H*)-ones (**2a,b**). Reaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride with **1** (*n*=1) gave 4',5'-cyclopentasp[iro-3*H*-indole-3,3'-(3*H*)-isoxazol]-2(1*H*)-one (**3c,d**), whereas **1** (*n*=2) gave 2,3*a*,4,5,6,7-hexahydrospiro[3*H*-benzisoxazole-3,3'-(3*H*)-indol]-2'(1'*H*)-ones (**3a,b**). Reaction with non-fluorinated **1** (*R*=H, *n*=2) afforded 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)-2'-oximeindole-2(1*H*)-one (**3a**) along with the spiro compound (**4a**).

The synthesis of spiro-indazoloindole involves the cyclocondensation of 3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene)indol-2(1*H*)-one with 4-fluorophenylsulphonyl hydrazide in ethanolic KOH medium. The formation of spiro compounds is evident from the ir, pmr and mass spectral studies. The ir spectra showed the disappearance of the exocyclic C=C at 1620 cm⁻¹, retention of NHCO at 1710 cm⁻¹ and appearance of the CN absorptions at 1590 cm⁻¹ indicating the participation of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl system involving cycloalkane ring. Pmr spectra showed a doublet at δ 4.13 for methine proton because this proton coupled with nearby methylene protons

with different dihedral angles. The methylene protons of cycloalkyl ring were obtained in the form of clusters, viz. δ 3.43 (2H, t, $N=C-CH_2$) and 1.42–2.36 (6H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$). Signals for the aromatic protons and the indole NH were observed at δ 6.88–8.02 and 9.01 respectively.

Further, the molecular ion peak was not observed in the mass spectrum of compound **2a**, other peaks were observed at m/z 280 ($M^+ - C_7H_5NO$) (8.2%), 256 ($280 - C_2H_4$) (3.6%), 255 ($280 - C_2H_5$) (9.5%), 254 ($M^+ - C_2H_6$) (57.8%) and 143 ($M^+ - C_{12}H_{15}FNO_2S$) (100%).

An analogous reaction of 3-(2-oxocyclopentylidene)indol-2(1H)-one and 4-fluorophenylsulphonyl hydrazide also furnished only one compound identified as 4',5'-cyclopentaspiro[3H-indole-3,3'(3H)-pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (**2c**) on the basis of analytical and spectral studies.

Reaction of fluorinated 3-(2-oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1H)-ones (**1**) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in dry pyridine in the presence of fused sodium acetate¹⁰ yielded exclusively the spiro compounds whereas the non-fluorinated analog **1** gave the oxime (**4a**) along with the spiro compound (**3a**) (Scheme 1). This reaction was also tried in ethanolic KOH medium^{7,11} but no reaction occurred even on refluxing upto 30 h. The ir spectra of the spiro compounds showed disappearance of exocyclic $C=C$ at 1620 and CO absorption at 1685 cm^{-1} and appearance of the absorptions at 1710 (NHCO) and 1640 cm^{-1} ($C=N$). The structure was further corroborated by pmr spectra and characteristic signals were observed at δ 1.42–1.62 (2H, m, $CHCH_2CH_2$), 2.04–2.62 (4H and 2H, m, CH_2CH_2 , in cyclohexyl and in cyclopentyl respectively), 3.22 (2H, t, $N=C-CH_2$), 4.13 (1H, dd,

CH), 7.26–8.02 (m, ArH) and 9.42 (1H, br, indole NH). The ^{13}C nmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of compound **3a** showed characteristic absorptions at δ 170.261 (CO), 157.236 ($C=N$), 150.126 (C-8'), 138.132 (C-6'), 125.023 (C-4), 122.182 (C-5'), 115.312 (C-9'), 113.092 (C-7'), 110.126 (spiro-carbon), 48.301–26.123 ppm (carbons of cyclohexyl ring). The mass spectrum of compound **3a** showed molecular ion peak at m/z 242 corresponding to its molecular weight with additional peaks at m/z 218 ($M^+ - CO$) and 216 ($M^+ - CN$). In case of fluorinated spiro compound **3b**, molecular ion peak was not observed and instead highest peak was observed at m/z 206 (83.1) due to the loss of C_4H_8 molecule. Other peaks were observed at m/z 208 ($M^+ - C_4H_4$) (18%), 207 ($M^+ - C_4H_5$) (68%), 169 ($207 - C_2N$) (12%), 147 ($M^+ - C_6H_{11}NO$) (14), 138 ($M^+ - C_7H_8NO$) (28) and 121 ($M^+ - C_7H_8FNO$) (82%).

The formation of 3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene)-2'-oximeindole-2(1H)-one (**3a**) was confirmed by the presence of exocyclic $C=C$ absorption at 1610 cm^{-1} along with 1700 (NHCO) and 1630 cm^{-1} ($C=N$) in the ir spectrum, and disappearance of the doublet of methine protons at δ 4.13 in the pmr spectrum.

The position of fluorine was confirmed by ^{19}F nmr spectra. Single fluorine at position-5 and CF_3 group at position-4 of indole ring appeared at δ –116 (**2b**, **2c**) and –57.32 (**4b**) ppm respectively. The single fluorine at the position-4 of phenyl ring in compounds **4a** and **4b** appeared at δ –102.36 ppm.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557

Scheme 1

spectrophotometer, ^1H and ^{19}F (TFA, CDCl_3) and ^{13}C nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer at 89.55, 84.25 and 22.49 MHz respectively, using TMS as internal standard for pmr and hexafluorobenzene as external standard for ^{19}F nmr, and mass spectra on Kratos MS-30 and MS-50 spectrometers at an ionisation potential of 70 eV.

3-(2-Oxocycloalkylidene)indol-2(1H)-one (1): The compounds were reported earlier⁴.

2, 3a, 4, 5, 6, 7-Hexahydro-2-(4-fluorophenylsulphonyl)spiro[3H-indazole-3,3'(3H)-indole]-2'(1H)-one (2a): A mixture of 3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene)indol-2(1H)-one (0.01 mol) and 4-fluorophenylsulphonyl hydrazide (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 16 h in ethanolic KOH. On keeping the reaction mixture for 24 h, the resulting light yellow solid was recrystallised from ethanol (2a).

Similarly, 4-trifluoromethyl-1-3-(2-oxocyclopentylidene)indol-2(1H)-one yielded a light brown compound, identified as 4',5'-cyclopenta-2'-(4-fluorophenylsulphonyl)-4-trifluoromethylspiro[3H-indole-3,3'-(3H)pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (2c) (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	n	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
2a	H	2	56	125	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$
2b	4- CF_3	2	58	150	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$
2c	4- CF_3	1	55	98	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{15}\text{F}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$
3a	H	2	35	120	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$
3b	5-F	2	60	280	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_2$
3c	5-F	1	58	300	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_2$
3d	4- CF_3	1	52	285	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{F}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$
4a	H	2	25	280 (decomp)	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

2,3a,4,5,6,7-Hexahydrospiro[3H-benzisoxazole-3,3'-(3H)indol]-2'(1H)-one (3a) and 3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene)-2'-oximeindol-2(H)-one (4a): A mixture of 3-(2-oxocyclohexylidene)indol-2(1H)-one (0.01 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (30 ml) and fused sodium acetate (1 g) was refluxed for 12 h. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and washed with dilute acetic acid. The solid thus obtained was subjected to

column chromatography. The benzene fraction gave light brown compound identified as 3a and the benzene-ethyl acetate (1:8) fraction gave a dark coloured compound identified as 4a.

Similarly, 3-(2-oxocyclopentylidene)indol-2(1H)-one gave 4',5'-cyclopentasp[3H-indole-3,3'(3H)-isoxazole]-2(1H)-one. Reaction with fluorinated cycloalkylidene derivatives yielded exclusively the spiro compounds (2b-e) (Table 1).

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